

Proposing Two New Holistic Development Models MPHD and MPRD for Indian Learning Ecosystems

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Abstract:- Learning is an indispensable part of any individual's life. Mental development is important not only for the progress of individuals, but also for organizations and in turn the society. However, adequate emphasis is not being laid on developing newer training & development models that incorporate the dynamically changing needs of the generation. The thesis brings into perspective a side of training models, which has been side-lined in the Indian education system.

In case of every individual, learning is a process affected by several entities together viz. parents, friends and family, teachers, neighbors, media and society at large. They are to be considered as learning inputs for an individual in this study. After analyzing the effect of each of these major inputs from a psychodynamic standpoint, some gaps in learning were observed. Post this analysis, two new models have been developed and the researcher proposes these models to be used by institutions, organizations and individual trainers for reference while designing training programs.

However, since the standard of living and psychology differs from society to society, these models would rely on the ability of trainers to adapt the models suitable for their target audience. For the first phase of research, the only focus here is on India and its learning systems.

Keywords:- Indian education ecosystem, learning and training models, holistic development, training and development, psychodynamics in learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

This Learning is a life-long process. An individual keeps learning throughout his life from the inputs received through his surroundings. Every experience, interaction creates a psychodynamic structure which then dictates the individual's behavior under any given circumstance. Thus, external factors play an important role in an individual's learning process, much more than internal factors. However, with the development of technology and outburst of social media, the sources of learning have shifted drastically.

India is a very diverse country. There is diversity in language, cultures, beliefs, deities, individual habits and social norms. With diversity comes a widely varied belief system and behavioral patterns. This variety has, over the years, shaped its people and their behaviors. The Indian belief system is highly influenced by its cultures. Until

1990, every diverse culture in India had its own belief and operating system because of which the impact of learning inputs had been limited to the surroundings. Hence to enhance the training development models was comparatively easier since the learning inputs were restricted geographically. Any errors in the learning could be easily identified and corrected in time.

However, with the Indian economy participating actively in globalization, the meddling of social media and the reliance on technology for our lives has increased which has drastically shifted the balance of impact that the learning inputs should have on a person at every stage in his life. Owing to the huge number of inputs, error correction has become a herculean task for today's trainers and training mechanisms. The resulting individuals have deviated much further from the ideally expected individual. Upon understanding the impact analysis of these modern inputs, the researcher has developed a structure for training and development of every individual, with an aim to mitigate the negative effects of the surrounding inputs. The researcher argues that when an individual uses his reference models, the impact of external inputs shall be minimum and the learning outcomes throughout his life shall be as expected.

II. NEED FOR INDIAN EDUCATION SYSTEM TO CHANGE

For over half a decade, Indian education has predominantly focused on skill development rather than learning and there is a viable reason for it. Indian population has had a lot of struggles since post-independence period. It took over 2 generations since 1947 to achieve a quality standard of living for common public. Today, still about 22% of the population is below poverty line. Hence, more importance has always been given to developing job skills rather than any other criteria.

However, since a decade ago, things have started changing rapidly. Since 2001, India has undergone a huge number of innovations in technology and as a result it has evolved into a powerful nation. The recent government policies are quite encouraging for entrepreneurs in order to improve the export-to-import ratio. The outburst of the telecom sector has created strong networking capabilities in the entire country. Since the standard of living of a major population has improved, the spending on education has also increased. Basic amenities are not a concern today for most individuals. But modern amenities breed modern problems.

The learning ecosystem in India has yet not changed its outlook. There is still a high focus on skill development rather than learning. The government’s draft articulation of liberal education is targeted towards the development of the “Skill India” project, which plans to provide skill development training to over 400 million people. While this is the perfect step to be taken for rural development and those below poverty line, but there is a second side to the society, which constitutes to more than 50% of the population which can contribute greatly to the true development of the country. These are people who have understood and are spending on quality education for their children. It is because of this population, that the learning and development industry has been flourishing since the year 2000.

However, there is a big need to change the mentality of this population which spends on education. Because the global standards of education focus on learning more than mere skill development, while Indian learning focusses only on skill development. Since 2015, there is a slight awareness in holistic development in some states, but the execution still hasn’t seen any glorious days. With the world becoming one big global economy today, technological luxuries reaching even the dark corners of the society, the whole world is open for this generation. While it means that the whole world is an opportunity today, it also implies that the whole world is open to compete in the same market. Thus, mere skills will only take individuals so far. There is a definite need for a wholistic development right from the very beginning to ensure a skilled, bright, focused and independent individual. As discussed in 2.4, the ultimate motive of learning and development is independence. With the era of struggle for basics being gone for the predominant Indian population, it is time to change the psychology behind learning. Holistic development is still considered to be a luxury which most Indians cannot afford. It must be considered as a necessity than a luxury if we need India to achieve higher status in the world rankings.

III. SHORTCOMINGS IN THE USUAL TRAINING METHODS

This Learning input, for this research, is defined as any experience, interaction or study that creates a skill or knowledge bank in an individual. In any individual’s life, there are many learning inputs viz. parents, teachers, surroundings, media etc. For any desired outcome, a systematic well-defined learning structure is imperative, one in which there is only a specified impact of every defined learning input.

Fig. 1 Ideal learning Process

Fig. 2 Deviated Learning Outcome

Thus, a scenario where parents and teachers only are supposed to be the two learning inputs should be a contained ecosystem where impact of other inputs should be zero. If any other input adds to the experience, the impact balance shifts and so does the resulting individual.

Figure 1 above shows the ideal learning process. There are no deviations in the learning. Pre-decided learning inputs are the only ones influencing the individual’s learning and hence the resulting individual is as expected.

Figure 2 shows the effect of deviation δ on the outcome, when other than expected inputs deviate the individual from the expected learning curve. A deviation input δ , in this research is defined as a form of unplanned and unwanted learning input that deviates the outcome of a planned learning process. A learner is defined as any individual who acquires knowledge from the trainer. It has been observed that parents and teachers although have been quite interested in teaching their children earlier than usual, however they are quite deviated from the “What to teach” factor. On a macroscopic level, it is evident that a major reason in this deviation is the deviation inputs are impacting the learning inputs. Thus, there is a deviation beginning right from the basic inputs only. Figure 3 shows a visual representation of this issue.

With the complexities in training increasing due to the world becoming one global economy, controlling these deviation inputs is highly implausible.

A simple solution to the problem of deviation inputs is to execute the learning process in a controlled atmosphere. By restricting the exposure of learners to learning inputs only, the outcome of learning can be achieved as desired. For achieving this, the control measures must be applied strictly to the learning process such that the only input that a learner receives is the pure learning input. This would result in the ideal learning outcomes, as shown in Fig. 1 earlier. The outcomes of such controlled systems have been found to be quite impressive. The Gurukul learning method in India and the trainings at Shaolin temple are excellent examples of closed group, controlled learning methodologies that are critically acclaimed by education experts all over the world. The encapsulation of the entire learning ecosystem ensures non-entry of deviation inputs into the system, thus leading to a high yield individual. The training delivery is completely authoritative in this case and the term of learning process is quite large. However, if we are to implement these systems into the current Indian education ecosystem, there are a few discrepancies observed which are discussed below:

- The method of delivery is completely authoritative. This makes it a one-way knowledge transfer rather than an interactive transfer. There is no feedback mechanism from learner to trainer for adapting the delivery according to learner’s innate abilities. Secondly, this form of delivery lays complete reliance of the trainer. In this case, any deviation input entering the trainer’s side (as shown in fig 3) is unaccounted for. This deviation will be passed on to the learners in the form of biases and beliefs, thus changing the outcome. Also, in absence of quality trainers, this mode of delivery would fail and specially in the case of Indian scenario where we face a shortage of quality trainers.
- When an individual is given a choice to select his or her actions while learning, development can be exponential. In the case of controlled δ systems, the freedom of choice becomes highly restricted. The controlled δ systems do result in highly skilled individuals, but in most cases, it would result in an increased stress since it is human psychology to be resistant to external discipline.

- Since these systems contain learners over a longer period to control δ , it is not possible to execute such training systems in Indian ecosystem for numerous reasons. Firstly, the creation of such encapsulated environment training systems would require a huge capital investment due to residential facilities, which is a burden for the investor. India is a country with approximately 60% rural economy and as of 2019, still over 22% of the entire population are below poverty line. Indian students face a lot of restrictions due to money shortage which makes these systems unavailable for commoners.

IV. SUGGESTED SOLUTION TO REDUCE THE IMPACT OF DEVIATION INPUTS

A. Adding Feedback and correctional inputs to learning:

Feedback from the output to the learning input again can help trainers assess the difference between expected and actual (deviated) outcome. Upon analyzing the difference, the impact of deviation inputs can be understood and corrected. This feedback, over the period, can be used to improve the program.

This corrected input (feedback) depends on the ability of the trainers to understand the exact difference between the ideal and actual outcome and provide corrected input. The newer models suggested further in the paper aim to enhance this exact ability of trainers in providing the correct feedback input to mitigate the deviation input impact. Also, the new models aim at mitigating trainer biases since learners can themselves use the references and provide self-feedback at many times.

B. Inducing negative experiences in learning:

Figure 5 below shows typical journey of learning from incompetence to competence by learning, studying, practicing and finally achieving proficiency post-implementing the learnt methods and getting feedback via experiences.

Without considering psychological elements, the proficiency curve would look somewhat like the graph in fig. 6 below.

The transition from incompetence to proficiency shall be very smooth and gradual as expected. However, when we analyze the whole learning from more of a psychodynamic standpoint, we get an explanation of today's generation's increase stress levels. Proficiency, firstly, is becoming quite subjective in the fast-moving world. From psychoanalyzing learner mindsets, it is easy for them to gain a false sense of proficiency as shown in figure 7 below:

Fig. 7 Psychological stages in learning

Pt. A is where training starts, and point C is the inflection point beyond which an individual starts to become proficient in the skills/knowledge imparted in the training. The first graph represents the case where learner achieves competence without facing negative outcomes. A more colloquial term for this is “beginner’s luck”. Every learning process encounters some negative outcomes, however in this case if a learner does not encounter any negative outcomes till the point of competence, he experiences a false sense of proficiency. Competency refers to knowing a skill. Proficiency refers to achieving mastery over time on that skill/content. And mastery can only be achieved when an individual ascertains the impact of both positive and negative aspects of the learning process. As seen in the first graph, if the learner has achieved competence and later experiences multiple negative outcomes, the drop from high to low is steeper than before. This is because the confidence built from competency without negative experiences builds a false sense of proficiency, which breaks down due to multiple negative experiences. When the learner comes across negative experiences during incompetency when confidence is not yet built, the drop is not low since the learner is prepared to fail initially. However, the confidence goes down steeply as the learner has developed the belief that he possesses enough knowledge on the subject and is able to practically apply it. Once a belief is developed, it becomes very difficult to comprehend the negative experiences. Confidence built after resolving problems not only teaches exception handling but builds a level of stronger confidence in self and the knowledge acquired.

The researchers here suggests that from a psychodynamic viewpoint, if the stage 4 (fig.5) includes both positive and negative experiences, some of which can be induced by the trainers, then the competence will look like the second graph fig. 7 which is why trainers should induce negative outcomes before learners achieve competence. Therefore, an understanding of psychology greatly aids in improving the training quality.

V. MPHD MODEL (0-16 YRS)

The term **MPHD** is the acronym for **Modern Personal Holistic Development**, a new learning framework designed by the researcher and is presented briefly through this paper. The researcher would like to emphasize the fact that the design, in entirety, and its liabilities lie with the researcher. MPHD is a suggestive model which puts together a framework for trainers to help in the design and delivery of their trainings. MPHD focusses on training individuals from 0-25 years primarily but can be used for practically any age group of learners.

The model is designed keeping in mind the problems faced by the current generation of learners and can be used for further generations by making the appropriate modifications from time to time. However, for this model to work the best, harmonization of all learning inputs must be obtained, which basically means that all learning inputs affecting an individual (parents, teachers, trainers etc.) must work together, provide feedback on each other’s learnings and help take appropriate corrective actions when problems are identified in a learner’s development outcomes. When a learner experiences uniformity and harmony in the entire learning environment, the effect of any deviation input is automatically mitigated to a large extent. The resulting individual in such a case offers the least resistance to change and demonstrates maximum loyalty towards the learning process. Plus, this effect is contagious i.e. the same positive learnings are passed on when one of the learners takes up a trainer’s role in future. Hence it is necessary to harmonize the learning inputs and work towards a common goal of the learner’s development while using the model’s reference.

The MPHD model defines a set of 6 different functional areas of development, and which further comprise of a total of 56 identified development parameters, deemed necessary for an effective holistic development of an individual, ideally for the first 16 years of his life when learning is the easiest. The researcher has already been implementing the model in schools and within a select few parent groups and getting transformative results.

The 6 major functional development areas in every child are:

- Personality - Handling own self
- Leadership - Handling others
- Team skills - Working with others
- Communication - Connecting with others
- Academics - Educating own-self better
- Sports and fitness - Physical & mental health

Fig. 8

The researcher suggests that during the first 16 years of an individual’s life, if all these parameters are developed even though partially, then the result would be a high octane, self-learning, highly motivated and directed individual capable naturally producing a much higher output than he could in his normal course of learning. This higher yield would prove beneficial to the industry and the society at large. However, it is imperative to understand that since most of the parameters in the model are interdependent, development efforts should be wide enough to cover them all. That is why this is a holistic development model. Let us now look at the brief significance of the parent development areas and a briefer interpretation of the parameters of the group:

A. Personality (Handling one self)

Personality or persona is the generally understood as an overall impression of a person on others. However, in the thesis, when we talk about personality, we talk about self. 16 qualities have been identified in this research and each comprises of a quality that makes up the total persona. The idea behind the development of this set of characteristics is to forge a strong character in the individual. Most characteristics in this set pertain to human attitude rather than aptitude. A strong attitude and character in an individual go a long way ahead in life. The main objective behind development of this set of parameters is the developing an independent thinking attitude in the learners.

The 16 parameters that make up the personality set are:

Activeness	Determination	Optimism	Self-awareness
Self-esteem	Listening	Self-Control	Self-motivation
Self-dependence	Emotional expression	Bounce-back attitude	Risk attitude
Emotional quotient	Body language	Creativity	Vocal modulation

Table 1

B. Leadership (Handling others)

A lot of researchers through time have advocated that leaders are not just born; they can also be created and a lot others advocate the opposite. However, the debate about whether leaders can be created or not is irrelevant to this study since the researcher argues that while not everyone can become a leader, but in the real world, every individual at some point in life, has to assume a leadership role either in his social or professional life. Besides, not all but quite a handful or leader qualities can be inculcated in every learner. These qualities are quite handy while facing real-world problems since “life” and “stress” seem to go hand-in-hand today. The study identifies 13 important traits that must be developed however partially in every learner. The prime objective behind the development of this set is to augment the personality set and preparing learners for exception handling.

The 13 parameters that make up the leadership set are:

Empathy	Social quotient	Networking	Intuitive-ness
Observation Skills	Patience	Gratitude	Decision making
Morality	Oratory	Planning	Problem solving
Argumentative capability	-		

Table 2

C. Team Skills (Working with others)

Building on the aforementioned statement that not everyone can be a leader, there will always be a big mass of team members who need to understand how to function as a team. With the corporate functionality leaning heavily on team structures, it is highly important to have individuals who truly understand how to work as a team. As easy as it seems, the researcher argues that while working in teams, a lot of personalities clash which is why it is essential to have good leaders. However, not every time will a team have the luck of being led by a good leader. In many situations, teams have to function without leaders or worse, under bad leadership. In such cases, individuals will have to assume dynamic different roles in order to create and ensure synergy in order to satiate the ultimate goal. Also, it is highly unlikely that a person stays a leader all throughout life. Every leader must at some time assume a team player role. Hence, development of this set of parameters (5 parameters) gains importance.

The 5 parameters that make up this set are:

Team player	Leading from behind	Dominance
Conflict resolution	Giving and forgiving	-

Table 3

D. Communication (Connecting with others)

There is no life without communication. Whether verbal or non-verbal, every individual communicates continuously. However, there are a lot of aspects to the world of communication. Very often, individuals find themselves creating first impressions on others and hence there are a lot of things that can be improved to create better impressions. Communication is not only important for creating first impressions, but it follows one like a shadow throughout life. The knowledge of communication, in most Indian education institutions, has been restricted to speaking fluent English. However, this study disintegrates communication into 7 parameters which are deemed important to the current generation. Objective of this set of development is to help develop all the facets of communication.

The 7 parameters that make up this set are:

Face-to-face interaction	Global language skills	Vocabulary	Negotiations
Assertiveness	Oratory	-	-

Table 4

E. Academics (Educating own self)

Often deemed to be the most important part by many and the only important by some, academics plays a strong role in the upbringing of a child. A strong academic track record might not always imply success in life, but it does imply that the individual has put this brain through a rigorous process of learning and is disciplined and focused. However, the study does not consider academics as a mere performance in formal education. Study identifies 8 different parameters that are to be developed along with formal studies. The researcher suggest that these parameters need to be inculcated during formal study life only so that the concept of education can be widened in the minds of the learners. Some of these parameters are complementary while some others are supplementary to the formal education. An individual with well-developed academic parameters (as per the definition in the study) can be assumed to have a better brain development than other learners. The parameters identified are so designed keeping in mind the future needs of the current generation learners.

The 8 parameters that make up this set are:

Intelligence quotient	General knowledge	Research capability	Quantitative aptitude
Critical thinking	Stress handling	Orientation & focus	Technology aptitude

Table 5

F. Sports & Fitness (Physical & Mental health)

A sound mind cannot function without a sound body. Perhaps the most important of all the parameter sets yet often the most neglected need of the current generation, is physical health. We have already emphasized the kinds of stresses that individuals go through during every phase of life today. In order to cope up with the ever-increasing stress, a strong level of physical fitness is of utmost importance. The whole unfortunate pandemic of Covid-19 has re-iterated the importance of physical fitness to the entire world. Also, innumerable studies have linked physical fitness with higher performance in academics and better mental abilities. While some studies argue that physical fitness does not have a comparable impact on individual performance in many walks of life, the fact still remains that an absence of sound physical fitness does affect the performance negatively. In order to augment all development efforts, sound body is a basic assumption. In this study physical fitness has been split into its 7 basic components, the research of which has been done with the help and under the guidance of K11 Fitness Academy, Mumbai.

The 8 parameters that make up this set are:

Strength	Cardiovascular endurance	Flexibility	Mobility
Speed – Agility & Reflexes		Stability	Nutrition

Table 6

G. Interdependence of development sets

It is imperative that these development parameters not be considered as individual sets but the whole model as one big training program. Each of the areas are interdependent on each other. As stated earlier, physical fitness is related to all other groups. Physical development augments every other aspect of human development. Hence the development of physical fitness parameters is very important since every other set depends on it. Leadership is augmented by personality traits since personal traits are very important in the evolution of an individual to a leader. Team skills and leadership are both dependent on effective communication. Leaders need to effectively communicate their visions, thoughts, strategies etc. with their team. Also, it is the responsibility of the team member to communicate their responses with the leader and with other team members. Academic development in this case of this study is augmented by all others and some parameters of it (like research capabilities and critical thinking) assist in building leadership skills. Stress management techniques are equally important in leadership, team skills and also developing personality. The key idea behind the entire MPHD model is to provide a guideline for institutions to create a more conducive to learning environment that is challenging and nurturing at the same time.

VI. MPRD MODEL (16-25 YRS)

The term **MPRD** is the acronym for **Modern Professional Development**. The focus of this second model is on developing an industry focus and upskilling the learners with skills required to dominate in their respective professional spheres. The effectiveness of MPRD model to a large extent depends on the success of its predecessor, the MPHD model discussed in the previous chapter. This is because the MPRD model assumes that a learner has passed through the MPHD model training, since this model does not include any personality development parameters. The entire and absolute focus is on developing industry-oriented skills and thinking (hence the name professional development). If there has been no exposure to the MPHD model previously, speed of professional development will be greatly affected since a non-trained individual is much more likely to be affected by deviation inputs during learning. In the practical world, some parameters generally are developed directly or indirectly in the first 16 years. Hence there is no harm in setting up this model of development from higher secondary or collegiate level, but the responsibility of personal development in this case shall lie well with the individual self.

The MPRD model is divided into 3 phases:

- Junior college/ Diploma Level (16 -18 years)
- Graduation/ Post-Graduation Level (18 - 24 years)
- Industry Fresher Level – First year of joining (25 years)

The prima facie important aim and outcome of each of these three phases can be briefly defined in the figure 11.1 below:

Fig. 9: Phases of MPD Model (16-25 years of age)

Upon successful completion of MPHD training, the next transformation that is needed for every individual is the evolution into a professional person, with soft & technical skills, broad understanding of the industry dynamics, business basics and creating strong interpersonal relations.

The challenge with developing any skill is that they it takes time to gain proficiency, through conscious and continuous efforts. But what skills do individuals develop at what age, is completely subjective to the field of their choice, their aspirations in their career and their expectations from their professional life. This selection is

crucial and must be made by careful analysis of self and the industrial environment. The below considerations are important to understand.

- The industry is ever so dynamic and requires regular updation of one's knowledge and skills if he must perform well. However, this knowledge building and skill development costs either time or money or both.
- Time Vs. Money equivalency – When there is less time to develop a skill, more money needs to be spent to develop it. Since time for error correction and experimentation is less, reliance is on hiring the expert and experienced trainers who cost more. Hence, a well devised learning strategy could utilize more time (learners can engage in self-learning and experimentation) but save a lot on the budget side.
- The researcher suggest that skills and knowledge should be categorized into two parts: compulsory general knowledge/skills (GKS) and situational knowledge/skills (SKS). GKS implies the general set of skills and knowledge that an individual needs to survive in the professional domain. If started early, suggestively right after schooling, these can be developed at a very low or no cost (in terms of money not time). The researcher suggests that the budget saved can be utilized for SKS spending, since SKS are those domain specific skills, the requirements of which arise dynamically as per the industry's needs from time to time.

With these considerations in mind, it is clear that in order to implement MPRD model on a larger scale in India (a cost-sensitive market), starting early is the only sane choice. To implement this program in association with education institutions all across India primarily where students come from economically challenged strata of the society is going to be a demanding task.

The focus of pre-graduation years should be completely on GKS instead of SKS. This is because setting the right orientation is the objective at this stage of development. We already discussed parameters like decision making, self-awareness, self-motivation and self-reliance in MPRD model. When individuals make their own decisions after self- and industry-analysis, they are definitely more motivated than making the decisions based on someone else's recommendation or coercion. The job of learning ecosystem at this stage of the MPRD model involves the following series of action steps:

- Step 1: Help the learners in exploring the industry from a practical standpoint.
- Step 2: Perform a guided SWOT of self and the industry.
- Step 3: Make informed decisions about the broad choice of domain. Functional roles need not be finalized yet.
- Step 4: Understand businesses in general from a macro perspective and skills that are needed in future. Understand where you would like to fit in the whole business mechanism.
- Step 5: Start working towards developing GKS, with overview learning of SKS (to broaden the understanding and assess the inclination).

VII. CONCLUSION

The MPRD and MPRD are two new proposed models that aim to enhance the quality of training for any trainer. These models can be adopted and adapted by the learning ecosystem of India (education institutions and corporate companies) to enhance the personal development of their learners/employees, which in turn shall benefit them and thus the society at large.

Since these models are proposed ones (previously non-existent and untested), the execution will definitely be a herculean task for the implementors. Care must be taken while developing training programs to include all the parameters in both the models and understand the interconnectivity of the parameters. Trainers must also be wary of any deviation inputs that can pass on to learners and take utmost care to remove personal biases while delivering training.

Through the new models proposed above, the researcher hopes to provide a robust yet flexible framework for designing and delivering training.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Alkire, S. (2002) *Valuing Freedoms: Sen's Capability Approach and Poverty Reduction*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- [2.] Becker, G. (1993) *Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education*, 3rd edn. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- [3.] Drèze, J. and Sen, A. (2002) *India: Development and Participation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [4.] Folbre, N. (1994) *Who Pays for the Kids? Gender and the Structures of Constraint*. New York: Routledge.
- [5.] Jaggard, A. (2002) 'Challenging women's global inequalities: Some priorities for Western philosophers', *Philosophical Topics* 30(2): 229–52.
- [6.] Menon, N. (2002) 'Universalism without foundations?', *Economy and Society* 31(1): 152–69.
- [7.] Sen, A. (2004) 'Elements of a theory of human rights'. *Philosophy and Public Affairs* 32(4): 315–56.
- [8.] UNICEF (2003) *The State of the World's Children 2004: Girls Education and Development*. New York: UNICEF.
- [9.] Thanky, P. (2013). *Education System in Present Scenario: Problems & Remedies*. *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, 3(7), 166-167. Retrieved September 19, 2017 from [https://www.worldwidejournals.com/indian-journal-of-applied-research\(IJAR\)/file.php?val=July_2013_137268633_9_45dd6_49.pdf](https://www.worldwidejournals.com/indian-journal-of-applied-research(IJAR)/file.php?val=July_2013_137268633_9_45dd6_49.pdf)
- [10.] Varghese, N.V., & J.B.G. Tilak. (1991). *The financing of education in India*. International Institute for Educational Planning. Retrieved September 19, 2017.
- [11.] Chahal, M. (2015). *Higher Education in India: Emerging Issues, Challenges and Suggestions*. *International Journal of Business Quantitative*

- Economics and Applied Management Research, 1(11), 67-74.
- [12.] Mohan, L. (2014). Integration of Skill with Higher Education. Asian Journal of Research in Business Economics and Management, 4(4), 27-37.
- [13.] Nussbaum, M (2000) Women and Human Development. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [14.] Schultz,T. (1963) The Economic Value of Education. New York: Columbia University.
- [15.] Vyas, H. S. (2014). Challenges Facing Management Education—An Indian Perspective. Asian Journal of Management, 5(2), 235-239.
- [17.] Mishra Sharda, (2006). UGC and Higher Education System in India. Book Enclare, Jaipur.302006
- [18.] Ramesh G. Indian Higher Education and the Challenges of Sustainability: An Analytical Note. International Journal of Social Science & Interdisciplinary Research 2013; 2(9).
- [19.] British council report. Understanding India: The future of higher education and opportunities for international cooperation, 2014
- [20.] Mukhopadhyay, M. (2016). Quality management in higher education. SAGE Publications India.